

Using the pH meter

Step	Task	Images	Comments
<p>Document title: Using the pH meter</p> <p>Laboratory location: University of Stavanger (UiS)</p> <p>Objective: This procedure describes the laboratory method used to measure pH for model fluids prepared in this thesis work. It includes electrode rinsing, calibration with pH 7 buffer, sample measurement, and cleaning/storage after use.</p>			
<p>Preparation before measurement testing</p>			
1.	Press “On/Off” to switch on the pH meter.		
2.	Place the pH electrode into a small empty beaker. Try to avoid letting it touch the glass. Rinse the electrode with distilled water and then dry it with paper.		To move the pH meter, hold the rod with one hand and then pull the pH meter to the position where you want to place it.
3.	Use the buffer solution and place the electrode in the solution.		

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4.	Press “Cal” and wait until it measures a pH of 7.		
5.	When a pH of 7 has been measured, remove the buffer solution from the pH meter and place an empty beaker back underneath. Rinse the electrode with distilled water and dry it afterward.		Remember to empty the beaker before rinsing again.

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Start of test			
1.	Place the pH electrode in the sample to be measured. Then press “Read” and wait until the measurement is completed. Record the pH value.		
Clean the pH meter.			
2.	Clean the electrode after the measurement in the same manner as described in Step 2. Remember to dry it after cleaning.		
3.	Place the pH meter back as shown in the figure.		
4.	Check for any spills and wipe them up if necessary. Rinse the beaker and leave it to		

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	dry. Press and hold "On" to switch off the pH meter.		